

As on 29-01-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended in order to add record of antinutrients available in crops into the knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several sources mentioning of the crops. The sources may be review papers, databases and web articles. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken. The suggested keyword is “scientific name” + “antinutrient”.
2. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. Prior to data entry, one should know the following:
 - **‘Antinutrient & Toxicity’** is the table for recording the reported factor, effect of the factor and the method of reduction for an individual organism.
 - Procedures of data entry into the database (how to enter the data into the table); user will be trained for the data entry before entering data.
2. IMPORTANT: Prior to data entry, one has to ensure that the antinutrient data of each crop that is going to be entered does not exist in record of the database.
3. There are 9 fields to be entered, four of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

3.1 Crop ID (compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

3.2 Part (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the specific parts of a crop that contain the Antinutrient & Toxicity.
- There are 20 parts of crops that may contain the Antinutrient & Toxicity.
- Enter new data if there is more than one part from the crop that contain Antinutrient & Toxicity.

3.3 Reported Factor (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the factors that contributed to the effect of Antinutrient & Toxicity.
-
- Eg: Saponins, Tannins, Phytate and etc.

3.4 Effect

- This is referring to the effect of Antinutrient & Toxicity of the crops toward the consumer of the crops.

3.5 Cause Toxicity

- This is referring to whether the factor of Antinutrient & Toxicity can cause toxicity.
- User have to tick on the column if the reported factor of Antinutrient & Toxicity are cause toxicity toward the consumers.

3.6 Cause Allergic Reaction

- This is referring to whether the factor of Antinutrient & Toxicity can cause Allergic reaction.
- User have to tick on the column if the reported factor of Antinutrient & Toxicity are cause allergic reaction toward the consumers.

3.7 Reduction Method

- This is referring to method to reduce the effect of Antinutrient & Toxicity factor.

3.8 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop itself.

3.9 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One MUST create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.